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Enhanced production of aromatic hydrocarbons and phenols by catalytic co-pyrolysis of fruit and garden pruning wastes

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24 **Abstract**

25 Nowadays, urban bio-wastes (food, park and garden residues) are mainly processed into
26 compost and biogas for energy recovery, or even directly landfilled without exploiting
27 their potential as feedstock for valuable products. As an alternative, this work reports a
28 comprehensive experimental study for their potential valorization *via* catalytic co-
29 pyrolysis. For that, different mixtures of fruit wastes (FW), a representative component
30 of food refuse, and garden pruning residues (GP) were co-pyrolyzed in presence of a
31 nano-ZSM-5 zeolite (and in absence of catalyst for comparison purposes) in an ex-situ
32 fixed-bed reactor to evaluate the occurrence of different interactions that may affect the
33 yield and properties of the pyrolysis bio-oil* (water-free basis). All pyrolysis fractions
34 were characterized and the composition of bio-oil* was exhaustively identified and
35 quantified, going further than the previous works devoted to the co-pyrolysis of
36 feedstocks comprising lignocellulose and fruit wastes usually performed at microgram
37 scale (using micropyrolysis), with intrinsic limitations in terms of the product yields and
38 properties determination. Thus, we found that the incorporation of higher FW amounts in
39 the feed mixture led to lower oxygen contents in the bio-oil*, improving its quality and
40 its potential use as bio-fuel. Moreover, the bio-oil* composition was notably narrowed to
41 marketable chemicals, both phenolic derivatives (cresols and phenol) and especially to
42 monoaromatics (mainly xylenes and trimethylbenzenes).

43 **Keywords:** Gardening pruning residues, fruit wastes, co-pyrolysis, nano-ZSM-5

44

45 **1. Introduction**

46 Urban bio-wastes disposal is one of the biggest environmental concerns nowadays due to
47 rapid population and economic growth as a consequence of the larger urbanization and
48 industrialization. [1] For this reason, their management is considered a priority by the EU
49 since they constitute the largest single fraction of municipal solid wastes (34 % on average
50 of the total waste stream) with a generation rate of approximately 88 Mt every year. [2]
51 The Waste Framework Directive [3] defines bio-residue as “biodegradable park and
52 garden residues, food or kitchen wastes, and similar residues from food processing plants.
53 Forestry or agricultural residues, manure, sewage sludge, or other biodegradable wastes
54 such as natural textiles, paper or processed wood are not included”. These bio-residues
55 are mainly disposed of by landfill and incineration or recycled *via* composting, with
56 negative environmental effects such as odors, fires, volatile organic compounds (VOCs’s)
57 emissions, groundwater contamination, etc. [4]

58 In this regard, the EU has set a target of recycling 65% of municipal waste by 2035, for
59 which new alternatives for the management of urban bio-wastes are required due to its
60 high generation rate. [2] In addition, urban bio-residues are considered a renewable source
61 of carbon-based products (chemical and fuels) and their management options must be
62 oriented to take advantage of the resources contained in them, helping to reduce the
63 dependency on fossil fuels and the release of carbon dioxide into the atmosphere. [5]
64 Thus, urban bio-residues can be effectively valorized through biochemical processes
65 (anaerobic digestion) or thermochemical technologies (gasification, or pyrolysis). [6,7]
66 Pyrolysis is a process of transforming organic bio-wastes that has recently attracted great
67 attention. [8] It consists of the thermal decomposition of organic matter at temperatures
68 of 400-700 °C under an oxygen-free atmosphere leading to the generation of a

69 carbonaceous solid (biochar), a liquid fraction (bio-oil), and non-condensable gases (CO₂,
70 CO, H₂, and light hydrocarbons), whose yields greatly depend on the reaction conditions.
71 [9-12] In particular, fast-pyrolysis has been the subject of extensive research as a means
72 of processing organic wastes, especially for converting lignocellulosic biomass into a
73 liquid bio-oil. [13,14] However, pyrolysis bio-oil is a complex mixture of oxygenated
74 compounds, which are present in a relatively small amount, hindering their commercial
75 application as a transportation fuel or as an industrial chemical feedstock. Thus, pyrolysis
76 bio-oils have low heating values (LHV~17-19 MJ/kg) in comparison with those typically
77 exhibited by fossil fuels (40-45 MJ/kg), as well as poor chemical stability and high
78 corrosivity and viscosity. [15,16] The properties of the bio-oil can be improved if oxygen
79 is removed from its composition by contacting the pyrolysis vapours with a catalyst bed,
80 which is commonly denoted as catalytic pyrolysis. Depending on the catalyst properties
81 (acidity, basicity, porosity, etc.), oxygenated compounds, including alcohols, acids,
82 ketones, furans, sugars, and lignin oligomers can be converted into high-value marketable
83 products, such as phenols, aromatics, and olefins. This is of great importance since they
84 are considered key platform molecules in different segments of the chemical or
85 petrochemical sectors and, in the case of aromatics, can also be used as additives in the
86 formulation of fuels, increasing the overall economic efficiency of the process. [17]
87 The applicability and feasibility of urban bio-residues pyrolysis strongly depend on waste
88 stream characteristics and composition. Most of the research carried out has been focused
89 on the study of pyrolysis of different individual bio-wastes fractions such as citrus wastes
90 [18], fruit residues [19], coffee and tea wastes [20], garden residues [19], or food wastes
91 from the municipal collection. [21-24] However, the separation of these individual
92 components is not easy, due to their similar density, and maybe not be necessary since

93 the co-processing of the whole bio-residues stream (mainly formed by food and garden
94 refuses) could help to ensure the feedstock supply for the future urban biorefineries and
95 to respond to the actual management requirements. [25,26] In this context, the pyrolysis
96 of heterogeneous urban bio-wastes mixtures arises as a promising alternative for the
97 valorization of the entire bio-waste stream, as through this process different types of raw
98 materials can be processed together. [27] In addition, during their co-processing, these
99 urban bio-wastes mixtures can generate molecular species that may further interact with
100 each other promoting the occurrence of beneficial effects that can improve the quality of
101 the pyrolysis bio-oil. [28] However, despite its potential interest, there is limited
102 information in the literature about the co-pyrolysis of lignocellulosic residues and food
103 wastes, especially when the bio-oil is the target product. Thus, most of the works devoted
104 to the co-pyrolysis of lignocellulosic materials and food residues are mainly focused on
105 the increase of the energy content of the gaseous phase. In this regard, Lee et al.
106 investigated the thermal co-pyrolysis of mixtures of food wastes with herbal medicine
107 [29] obtaining a gaseous fraction with higher H₂ content than that produced during the
108 individual pyrolysis of each feedstock. Similar findings were also recently observed by
109 the same research group during the thermal co-pyrolysis of food wastes with wood bark.
110 [30] Likewise, Nagy et al. studied the temperature and the heating ramp during the thermal
111 co-pyrolysis and co-gasification of food wastes and woody biomass to assess their
112 influence on the yield and heating value of the gaseous fraction. [31] These research
113 works have studied thermal processing of different bio-residues mixtures, without
114 evaluating, in any case, the presence of a catalyst.

115 The number of publications is even more limited when the co-pyrolysis process is aimed
116 at the production of a liquid bio-oil. To the best of our knowledge, just one publication,

117 reported by Zhang et al. [32], investigated the bio-oil features during the catalytic co-
118 pyrolysis of a lignocellulosic material (corn stalk) with food wastes. These authors
119 evaluated the effect of the temperature on the production of aromatic hydrocarbons and
120 on the H/C_{EFF} ratio using a microcrystalline ZSM-5 zeolite as catalyst. However, this was
121 an analytical study performed on a pyrolyzer coupled to a GC/MS analyzer, and no
122 information on how the co-pyrolysis and the zeolite utilization influence the bio-oil mass
123 yield was discussed, providing only partial information about the effectiveness and
124 viability of the process. In addition, the aromatic composition given was based on the
125 relative area of the chromatograms, being a semiquantitative approach. Furthermore, no
126 information about the presence or composition of other organic compounds typically
127 contained in a pyrolysis bio-oil (acids, furan, phenolics, etc) was described.

128 With this background, this work investigates the catalytic co-pyrolysis of two real urban
129 bio-wastes, gardening pruning residues (GP) and fruit wastes (FW), which are one of the
130 main components of kitchen wastes together with vegetables. [33] In particular, the role
131 of the proportion of each bio-waste in the feedstock as well as of the incorporation of an
132 acidic catalyst (a nanocrystalline ZSM-5 zeolite) on the yield and properties of the
133 pyrolysis bio-oil has been investigated. For that purpose, reaction parameters, such as
134 mass yields and elemental composition of all pyrolysis products as well as other advanced
135 process indicators, including deoxygenation selectivity and mass concentration of
136 compounds in bio-oil detectable by GC-MS have been deeply assessed. The co-
137 processing of both feedstocks, having different chemical and structural compositions, in
138 presence of a ZSM-5 nanozeolite promotes the occurrence of beneficial effects between
139 the pyrolysis products of each bio-waste. Thus, the bio-oils so-obtained show lower
140 oxygen contents and increased concentrations of valuable monoaromatic hydrocarbons

141 (MAH) and phenolics derivatives, compared to those obtained in the pyrolysis of pure
142 GP, but showing higher bio-oil* yields than those attained when only FW are used as
143 feedstock.

144 **2. Materials and Methods**

145 *2.1. Catalyst sample*

146 The zeolite employed as catalyst was a nanocrystalline ZSM-5 (n-ZSM-5) commercially
147 available from CLARIANT (ref. HCZP90, [Si/Al]_{MOL}= 42). Previously to the catalytic
148 assays, the sample was granulated by pressure and then crushed and sieved in a particle
149 size range from 0.18 to 0.25 mm.

150 Both Si and Al contents and, accordingly, the real molar Si/Al ratio, were calculated by
151 inductively coupled plasma-optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) in a Perkin Elmer
152 Optima 7300 AD analyzer. Previously, the sample was digested in an acidic solution
153 (HF/HNO₃) using an Anton Paar MW3000 microwave. The zeolite crystallinity was
154 evaluated by powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) in the 2θ range of 5–50° in a Philips PW
155 3040/00 X'Pert MPD/MRD diffractometer equipped with a linear detector that was
156 operated at 45 kV and 40 mA using Cu Kα radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) using a step size of
157 0.013° and time per step of 39.525 s. Argon adsorption-desorption isotherms at 87 K were
158 measured in an AUTOSORB iQ Analyser System from Quantachrome Instruments.
159 Before the analyses, ca. 250 mg of sample were outgassed at 300 °C under vacuum for 3
160 h. The overall acidity of the catalyst was determined by temperature programmed-
161 desorption of NH₃ (TPD-NH₃) in a Micromeritics AUTOCHEM 2910 analyzer following
162 the procedure previously described in earlier work. [34]

163

164

165 *2.2. Biomass feedstock*

166 Two different feedstock were used in the pyrolysis tests: garden pruning residues (GP)
167 and fruit wastes (FW) as a representative component of food residues. Garden pruning
168 wastes come from the municipal pruning works of the Community of Madrid and were
169 kindly provided by CIEMAT; whereas fruit residues (mainly peels and seeds) were
170 collected from the canteen of IMDEA Energy Institute for one month.

171 Both residues were dried overnight at 105 °C and then grounded and sieved to a particle
172 size in the range of 0.5-1 mm.

173 *2.3. Pyrolysis tests*

174 Pyrolysis tests of both residues were carried out in a lab-scale fixed-bed reactor, whose
175 schematic representation and technical specifications were detailed in the Supplementary
176 Material document (see Fig. S1). [35,36] All the reaction tests were performed under an
177 oxygen-free environment and atmospheric pressure using temperatures of 500 °C and 450
178 °C, respectively, for the thermal and catalytic zones. As a general procedure, 5 g of the
179 pre-dried bio-wastes mixture were placed in the feedstock container. Then, the complete
180 reaction system was purged with N₂ to ensure an inert atmosphere using a N₂ flow of 100
181 mL/min. Once both reaction temperatures were stabilized, the feedstock mixture was
182 discharged into the reactor, being thermally decomposed to yield a solid residue (bio-
183 char) that was accumulated in the thermal zone whereas the pyrolysis vapours left the
184 reactor through a condensation trap (passing through the zeolite bed, in the case of the
185 catalytic assays), where the bio-oil was collected. The non-condensable gases were
186 accumulated in a gas totalizer to be further analyzed by GC.

187 To elucidate the role of each type of waste on the product's yields and properties, four
188 feedstock compositions were tested: one for each pure waste and two blends with 20 and

189 40 wt.% of fruit wastes, respectively. Both non-catalytic (thermal) and catalytic reactions
190 were carried out in all cases. For catalytic pyrolysis tests, the catalyst to feedstock ratio
191 employed was 0.4 g/g (2 g of n-ZSM-5). The experiments were identified indicating first
192 the type of reaction (TP for thermal pyrolysis and CP for catalytic one), followed by the
193 composition of the feedstock. For example: “TP 100GP” corresponds to thermal pyrolysis
194 assay of 100 wt.% of garden pruning, while “CP 60GP/40FW” represents the catalytic
195 pyrolysis of 60 wt.% of garden pruning and 40 wt.% of fruit wastes.

196 *2.4. Characterization of raw bio-residues and pyrolysis products*

197 Proximate analyses of both bio-residues and bio-chars were carried out following
198 European standard procedures. Volatile matter, moisture, and ash contents were estimated
199 following the norms UNE-EN ISO 18134- 1:2016, UNE-EN ISO 18123:2016, UNE-EN
200 ISO 18122:2016, respectively. The fixed carbon was calculated by the difference of those
201 values regarding the initial sample weight. Elemental CHN analyses of raw bio-wastes
202 and pyrolysis products (biochar, bio-oil, and coke) were performed in a Thermo Scientific
203 micro-elemental analyzer. The oxygen (O) content was calculated by difference, after
204 subtracting the ashes, if any. The composition of both bio-residues samples (cellulose,
205 hemicellulose, lignin, extractives, and ash), as well as carbohydrate analysis, was
206 determined using an adapted procedure from the National Renewable Energy Laboratory
207 (NREL; Colorado, EE UU). Details about such procedures can be consulted in the
208 literature. [37] On the other hand, the thermal decomposition of both bio-residues was
209 evaluated in a NETZSCH 449 Thermobalance using a heating rate of 10 °C/min up to 700
210 °C under an inert atmosphere. Finally, the yield of the coke formed over the zeolite was
211 determined by combustion heating the spent catalyst to 900 °C at 10 °C/min in an air
212 atmosphere using the above-mentioned thermobalance [36] while its composition was

213 determined by CHN elemental analysis. The mass yield (Y_{wi}) of the different pyrolysis
214 products was determined according to the procedure previously reported. [36]
215 The gaseous fraction evolved from the reactor was analyzed by GC in a dual-channel
216 Agilent CP-4900 Micro-GC, equipped with two different columns, a CP-MolSieve 5 Å
217 and a P-PoraPLOT Q, using He as carrier gas. Both columns were previously calibrated
218 with gas mixtures containing CO, CO₂, H₂ and light paraffins and olefins (C₁-C₄) to
219 quantify their yields.

220 The water concentration of the bio-oil was measured by Karl–Fischer titration using a
221 Mettler-Toledo V20S compact volumetric titrator. The organic composition of the bio-
222 oil was examined by GC-MS employing a Bruker® SCION 436-GC analysis. The
223 identification of the compounds was carried out applying the NIST EI-MS v 2.0 spectral
224 library. The identified compounds (minimum correlation match of 700) were classified
225 according to their organic functionality as short-chain carboxylic acids (AC), aldehydes
226 (ALD), alcohols (ALC), ketones (KET), furans (FUR), oxygenated aromatics (OAR),
227 aromatic hydrocarbons (AH) and sugars (SUG). In addition, the family of aromatic
228 hydrocarbons was divided into monoaromatic (MAH) and polyaromatic hydrocarbons
229 (PAH), respectively; while that of oxygenated aromatics was distributed into several sub-
230 groups: phenols (PHE), guaiacols (GUA), syringols (SYR), catechols (CAT), and
231 methoxybenzenes (METH). The concentration of the identified products was determined
232 by external calibration of the most abundant components of each family, including a total
233 of 15 compounds (acetic acid, 2-cyclopenten-1-one, furfural, phenol, guaiacol, cresol,
234 vanillin, eugenol, trimethoxytoluene, 3-methoxycatechol, syringol, toluene, xylene,
235 trimethylbenzene and levoglucosan), which represents more than 60 % of the total area

236 of the GC chromatogram. The response factors of the remaining compounds were
237 estimated as the average response factor of the corresponding family.

238 In addition, the bio-oil fraction detectable by GC-MS, denoted as “*Bio-oil* quantified*
239 *fraction*”, was calculated as the percentage of the overall mass of the components
240 detected by GC-MS (using the above-mentioned calibration curves) with respect to the
241 total amount of the obtained bio-oil*.

242 The selectivity for the removal of oxygen from the bio-wastes or *ODS* (overall
243 deoxygenation selectivity) by means of dehydration, decarbonylation, or decarboxylation
244 was estimated as follow:

$$245 \quad ODS (\%) = \frac{O_k(g)}{O_f(g)} \cdot 100 \quad (3)$$

246 where O_k denotes the oxygen in the form of H₂O in the bio-oil and as CO or CO₂,
247 previously quantified in the gas fraction and O_f represents the oxygen content of the
248 biomass feedstock. Similarly, the catalytic deoxygenation selectivity (*CDS*) was
249 calculated considering the incremental generation of H₂O, CO, and CO₂ in the catalytic
250 experiments once the corresponding contribution of the thermal pyrolysis assay was
251 subtracted.

252 **3. Results and discussion**

253 *3.1. Catalyst characterization*

254 A nanocrystalline ZSM-5 zeolite (n-ZSM-5), provided by Clariant, is used as catalyst in
255 the present study. The XRD pattern of n-ZSM-5 displayed in Fig. S2 presents the
256 characteristic diffraction peaks of the MFI zeolitic structure showing a high crystallinity
257 degree. This zeolite exhibits a nanocrystalline nature with crystals in the range of 40–80
258 nm, as denoted by the TEM images depicted in Fig. S3. The textural properties, estimated
259 from Ar adsorption-desorption isotherms at 87 K, are collected in Table S1. As observed,

260 this sample exhibits a specific surface area of 445 m²/g with a significant contribution of
261 external and mesoporous surface area (127 m²/g) due to the formation of an interparticle
262 porous system because of the agglomeration of the zeolitic nanocrystals. These features
263 provide a decreased diffusion length and fully accessible active sites on the outer surface
264 of the zeolite for the processing of the bulky molecules present in the pyrolysis vapours.
265 On the other hand, the aluminium amount of this sample was determined by ICP-OES,
266 showing a Si/Al molar ratio of 42. The acid properties of the zeolite were evaluated by
267 NH₃-TPD analysis (Fig. S4). The desorption profile displays two desorption peaks, one
268 at about 180 °C corresponding to weak acidic sites, and a broader one centered at around
269 360 °C ascribed to stronger acid sites. The overall acidity value is 0.28 mmol NH₃/g,
270 which agrees with its Al content.

271 Regarding these properties, this nano-ZSM-5 can be considered as a promising catalyst
272 for bio-oil upgrading, since they combine, in a sole material, the improved mass transfer
273 characteristic from their nanocrystalline nature with the acidity and high intrinsic activity
274 of zeolites.

275 *3.2. Properties of the fruit wastes (FW) and garden pruning (GP) feedstock*

276 The valorization of different mixtures of fruit wastes and garden pruning residues via
277 thermal and catalytic fast co-pyrolysis has been deeply investigated to envisage the
278 occurrence of beneficial effects that could affect the yield and composition of the bio-oil.
279 Garden pruning residues were obtained from trimming and cleaning works of gardens
280 and parks containing leaves, branches and grass wastes. Fruit wastes represent the largest
281 group in household food refuse and, for this research, were selectively collected. First,
282 both raw materials were characterized to determine their chemical and structural

283 composition. Proximate and ultimate analyses, the high heating values as well as the
 284 biopolymer and extractives contents of both bio-wastes are given in Table 1.

285

286 **Table 1.** Chemical and structural composition of the fruit wastes (FW) and garden
 287 pruning (GP).

	Fruit Wastes (FW)	Garden Pruning (GP)
Moisture (wt.%)	1.1	1.2
Proximate analyses (wt.% db ^a)		
Volatile matter	70.5	82.5
Ash	5.5	3.3
Fixed carbon	24.0	14.2
Elemental analyses (wt.% daf ^b)		
C	51.5	50.1
H	6.3	6.1
N	1.3	1.4
O	40.9	42.4
HHV (MJ/kg)	19.9	19.5
Structural Components (wt.%)		
Extractives	60.2	9.3
Cellulose	9.2	37.2
Hemicellulose	6.7	14.0
Lignin	15.6	29.1
Acetyl groups	1.6	4.8
Others	1.2	2.3

288 ^a db: dry basis; ^b daf: dry and ash-free basis

289

290 Prior to these analyses, GP and FW residues were subjected to a pre-drying process,
291 reducing the moisture content to values close to 1 wt.%. As observed, both bio-residues
292 show intermediate carbon (51.5-50.1 wt.%) and high oxygen contents (40.9-42.4 wt.%),
293 with no significant differences between them. Hydrogen and nitrogen percentages are
294 also quite similar with values in the range of 6.1-6.3 and 1.3-1.4 wt.%, respectively.
295 Interestingly, the volatile matter of GP is significantly higher than that obtained for FW
296 (82.5 vs 70.5 wt.% db), which is expected to have an important role in the bio-oil yield.
297 The main difference between GP and FW bio-residues is found in the structural
298 composition. GP residue is mainly comprised of cellulose (37.2 wt.%), hemicellulose (14
299 wt.%), and lignin (29.1 wt.%) as a typical lignocellulosic feedstock, with a relatively low
300 contribution of extractives (9.3 wt.%), acetyl groups (4.8 wt.%), ashes (3.3 wt.%) and
301 other compounds (2.3 wt.%). In contrast, the amounts of cellulose, hemicellulose, and
302 lignin in fruit wastes are considerably lower (9.2, 6.7, and 15.6 wt.%, respectively),
303 exhibiting a high extractives content of 60.2 wt.%, such as pectin, lipids, proteins, and
304 amino acids. [38]

305 The thermal behavior of both bio-residues was initially studied by TG-DTG analyses
306 under inert atmosphere (Fig. 1). In the DTG curve of garden pruning residues, a wide
307 peak can be observed in the range of 240-480 °C (with a maximum at 384 °C) attributed
308 to the overlapped weight losses of hemicellulose, cellulose, and lignin, which decompose
309 in the temperature intervals of 220-315 °C, 315-400 °C, and 200-700 °C, respectively.
310 [39] The extractives weight loss also contributes to the DTG signal in the whole
311 temperature range, overlapping with those of the previous biopolymers as reported by
312 Qiao et al. [40], who showed that N-free extracts, lipid, and proteins decomposed from
313 200 to 600 °C.

314

315 **Fig. 1.** Thermogravimetric analyses of fruit wastes (FW) and garden pruning residues
 316 (GP). Analyses conditions: 100 mL/min Ar; heating rate of 10 °C/min, from room
 317 temperature to 700 °C.

318

319 On the other hand, in the DTG curve of fruit wastes, two peaks are clearly distinguished,
 320 centered at 231 °C and 337 °C, respectively. The first one, which does not appear in the
 321 DTG profile of GP, is assigned to the thermal decomposition of pectin, indicating that
 322 this is the main component of the extractives fraction in this bio-residue. [38] Pectin is
 323 a heteropolysaccharide mostly constituted by alternating galacturonic acid and
 324 rhamnose units and is usually found in fruit peels. The second peak corresponds to the
 325 overlapped thermal degradation of lignocellulose biopolymers and other extractives,
 326 such as lipids, proteins, and cellulose. [40,41]

327

328

329

330 3.3. Thermal and catalytic pyrolysis assays of garden pruning and fruit wastes mixtures

331 Fig. 2A shows the mass yields, referred to the initial weight of the feed mixture, of the
332 pyrolysis fractions (char, bio-oil*, water, gases, and coke) in the thermal (TP) and
333 catalytic pyrolysis (CP) experiments of GP and FW blends.

334 For thermal pyrolysis assays, char yields increase with the FW content in the feed mixture
335 (from 29 to 36.5 wt.%), which is accompanied by a diminution in the bio-oil* (water-free
336 basis) production (from 43 to 32 wt.%). This effect can be related to the lower volatile
337 matter share of FW compared to GP (70.5 vs 82.5 wt.%, Table 1).

338 Both water and gas fraction yields increase slightly with the proportion of FW, being
339 noteworthy the growing trend in the CO₂ production and the opposite behaviour of CO
340 (Fig. 2B), which denotes that, during the thermal pyrolysis assays, an increasing amount
341 of FW favours the deoxygenation of the feedstock *via* decarboxylation.

342

343

344 **Fig. 2.** Mass yields of pyrolysis products (A) and components of the gaseous fraction (B)
 345 in thermal (TP) and catalytic pyrolysis (CP) of fruit wastes (FW) and garden pruning (GP)
 346 mixtures. GO: gaseous olefins (C₂-C₄), GP: gaseous paraffins (C₂-C₄).

347

348 These results agree with the results found by Aburto et al. in their investigation about the
 349 thermal decomposition of pectin through coupled TGA-DSC/FT-IR analyses. [42] They
 350 established that pyrolytic decomposition of pectin occurs by a complicated series of
 351 consecutive and simultaneous reactions promoted at different temperatures: (i)
 352 dehydration, below 100 °C; (ii) primary depolymerization, between 100-210 °C,
 353 consisting of the breaking of bonds between carbohydrate molecules; (iii) secondary

354 decomposition of the monomers of pectin, between 250-580 °C, and (iv) devolatilization
355 of bio-char residues, above 600 °C. They also observed that for temperatures below 200
356 °C and in the range of 300-600 °C, no CO was detected in the evolved gases stream,
357 decarboxylation (formation of CO₂) being the main deoxygenation pathway. This is a
358 favourable aspect since the pyrolysis vapours upgrading *via* decarboxylation is preferred
359 to decarbonylation in terms of mass and energy efficiencies. These tendencies result in
360 an increase of the carbon content (from 57.6 to 66.5 wt.%, Table 2) together with a
361 reduction of the oxygen concentration (from 34 to 22.4 wt.%, Table 2) in the bio-oil* as
362 the FW proportion in the feedstock increases from 0 to 100 wt.%. Consequently, the bio-
363 oil* HHV is also progressively enhanced, from 25.2 to 30.7 MJ/ kg, being significantly
364 superior to the values of the raw bio-residues (~19.9 MJ/kg, Table 1).

365 In the catalytic experiments, the char yields are quite similar to those obtained for thermal
366 experiments with the same feed, exhibiting an increasing trend with the FW content. This
367 is an expected finding since it is produced in the thermal zone of the reactor and, therefore,
368 it is not affected by the presence of the zeolite. Nevertheless, some amount of coke is
369 deposited over the zeolite surface with yields varying from 2.5 to 3.5 wt.% (Fig. 2A).

370 Moreover, the catalyst addition produces an important growth of the yields of the gas
371 fraction, varying from ~13 in TP to 20.5 wt.% in CP, as a consequence of the occurrence
372 of cracking and deoxygenation reactions of the primary pyrolysis vapours catalyzed by
373 the acid sites of the zeolite. CO₂ is the predominant component in the gas fraction,
374 although CO production also increases compared with the thermal assays, revealing that
375 the zeolite promotes both decarbonylation and decarboxylation reactions (Fig. 2B).

376

377 **Table 2.** Water content, elemental composition and, HHV of the bio-oil* produced in
 378 thermal (TP) and catalytic pyrolysis (CP) of fruit wastes (FW) and garden pruning (GP)
 379 mixtures

Experiment	Water content (wt.% liq. fraction)	Elemental composition (wt.% bio.oil db ^a)					HHV (MJ/kg _{bio-oil} , db)
		C	H	N	S	O	
		TP 100GP	27.2	57.6	7.3	1.1	
TP 80GP/20FW	29.7	60.2	7.4	1.5	0.0	31.0	26.5
TP 60GP/40FW	31.8	60.9	7.7	1.9	0.0	29.5	27.3
TP 100FW	35.7	66.5	8.3	2.8	0.0	22.4	30.7
CP 100GP	43.9	69.4	8.3	1.7	0.0	20.6	31.9
CP 80GP/20FW	46.5	69.4	8.8	2.4	0.0	19.5	32.5
CP 60GP/40FW	47.2	74.8	8.9	2.0	0.0	14.4	35.0
CP 100FW	51.2	74.5	9.8	3.0	0.0	12.7	36.2

380 ^a db: dry basis

381

382 The yield of gaseous paraffins (GP) and, especially, of gaseous olefins (GO) also
 383 augments with the catalyst incorporation. This fact can be assigned to the occurrence of
 384 a variety of reactions, such as cracking and deoxygenation of light oxygenates originated
 385 from the decomposition of the structural components (holocellulose, lignin, or pectin)
 386 present in the raw bio-wastes as well as dealkylation processes of the resultant bio-residue
 387 fragments, promoted by the zeolite catalyst. [2] Nevertheless, the overall yields of these
 388 gaseous hydrocarbons are less than 2.5 wt.%.

389 On the other hand, the presence of the zeolite also raises the water yields, increasing from
390 16-17 wt.% in TP to ~22-23 wt.% in CP assays, due to the occurrence of dehydration and
391 condensation reactions, although no significant changes are observed with the FW share.
392 The higher generation of water in the catalytic assays provokes the segregation of the bio-
393 oil in two phases, aqueous and organic. The aqueous phase is mostly constituted by water
394 and hydrophilic compounds, such as acids and light oxygenates, whereas the organic
395 fraction has a small water content (< 7 wt.%) and is mainly formed by relatively
396 hydrophobic compounds. As a consequence of the higher water and gases production, the
397 yield of the organic liquid phase (bio-oil*) is significantly reduced in the catalytic
398 experiments. However, the catalytic promotion of deoxygenation (dehydration,
399 decarboxylation, and decarbonylation) and cracking reactions produces an important
400 reduction in the oxygen share in the bio-oil* elemental composition (Table 2).
401 Consequently, the HHV of the bio-oil* improves significantly. This effect is favoured
402 with the introduction of FW in the feed mixture, increasing from 31.9 MJ/kg, when only
403 GP is used as feedstock, up to 36.2 MJ/kg, when pure FW is fed into the reaction system.
404 The variation of the bio-oil* elemental composition can be appreciated in the Van
405 Krevelen graph plotted in Fig. 3A, which shows the evolution of the bio-oil* composition
406 in terms of the “effective H/C ratio”, defined as $(H-2O-3N)/C$, which takes into account
407 the available hydrogen assuming that all the oxygen present in the bio-oil would be
408 eliminated in the form of water, vs the O/C ratio. [35,43] As observed, higher FW
409 proportions in the feed mixture lead to lower O/C ratios and an improvement of the
410 effective H/C ratio. This fact clearly denotes that, in the catalytic tests, the structural
411 composition of this bio-residue, mainly comprised of pectin and other extractives,
412 facilitates the bio-oil* deoxygenation. Nevertheless, according to previous results, this

413 bio-oil* upgrading is accompanied by a decrease in its mass yield. In this sense, the
 414 effectiveness of the process can be evaluated through the relationship between the
 415 variation of the oxygen content and the mass yield of the bio-oil* fraction, as illustrated
 416 in Fig. 3B. Here, it is clear that the catalyst enhances the bio-oil* deoxygenation and,
 417 therefore, the bio-oil quality in terms of stability and utilization as fuel.

418
 419 **Fig. 3.** Thermal and catalytic bio-oils*: Van Krevelen graph (A) and oxygen
 420 concentration versus bio-oil* mass yields (B).

421
 422 The overall deoxygenation selectivity values (ODS) *via* dehydration, decarboxylation,
 423 and decarbonylation were estimated from the yields of H₂O, CO₂, and CO, respectively,

424 being plotted in Fig. 4A. As observed, dehydration is the main deoxygenation route in
 425 thermal assays, with values around 61-64 %. No clear tendency can be appreciated with
 426 the composition of the bio-residue mixture used as feedstock. Decarboxylation is the
 427 second deoxygenation pathway, which is favoured by increasing the proportion of FW in
 428 the bio-residue feedstock, with values in the range of 27-34 %. This higher generation of
 429 CO₂ with the FW content could be related to the degradation of extractives, in particular,
 430 pectin as found in the TG-DTG analyses previously shown in Fig. 1.

431
 432 **Fig. 4.** Overall deoxygenation (ODS) (A) and catalytic deoxygenation (CDS) (B)
 433 selectivity in thermal and catalytic pyrolysis of fruit wastes (FW) and garden pruning
 434 (GP) mixtures.

435 The catalytic deoxygenation selectivity was also determined, from the incremental
436 production of H₂O, CO, and CO₂ in the catalytic tests (Fig. 4B). In all cases, dehydration
437 is still the predominant deoxygenation route, which slightly decreases with the FW
438 content in the feed mixture, exhibiting values comprised between 50-60 %.
439 Decarbonylation and decarboxylation routes are promoted in less extension, showing
440 values in the range of 14-20 % and 20-30 %, respectively, the latter increasing with the
441 FW proportion in the feed mixture, while decarbonylation shows a maximum for CP
442 60GP/40FW mixture. Therefore, the presence of the zeolite catalyst does not alter the
443 overall trend of the deoxygenation selectivity (decarbonylation < decarboxylation <
444 dehydration).

445 The bio-oil* molecular composition was assessed by GC-MS analyses. This analytical
446 technique is usually applied as a semi-quantitative method that provides the results in the
447 form of the relative area of the detected compounds. However, in this research, the
448 equipment was previously calibrated to determine the response factors of the main
449 components in each family. The GC-MS calibration allowed to quantify, not only the
450 concentration of each compound in the bio-oil* but also the fraction of bio-oil* that can
451 be detected (“*Bio-oil* quantified fraction*”) by this technique (Fig. 5A). This parameter
452 was estimated as the percentage of the overall mass of the components detected by GC-
453 MS with respect to the total amount of the obtained bio-oil and is not usually reported in
454 the literature devoted to the pyrolysis of organic wastes. As observed in Fig. 5A, the
455 quantified fraction is about 40 wt.% of the bio-oil* mass yields in the thermal experiment
456 of pure GP, decreasing up to 30 wt.% when 20 wt.% of FW is introduced into the feed
457 mixture. This fact denotes that the presence of FW favours the formation of heavy
458 compounds, which agrees with their higher fixed-carbon content determined by

459 proximate analysis. The quantified fraction of the bio-oil* is enhanced with the presence
460 of n-ZSM-5, which can be attributed to the ability of this zeolite to convert oligomers and
461 heavy species, although these values follow a decreasing trend from 50 to 45 wt.% when
462 FW share increases. [32,36]

463 Fig. 5B represents the concentration of the main families of components present in both
464 thermal and catalytic bio-oils*. The detected compounds are grouped, regarding their
465 organic functionality, into carboxylic acids (AC), aldehydes (ALD), alcohols (ALC),
466 ketones (KET), furans (FUR), anhydrosugars (SUG), oxygenated aromatic compounds
467 (OAR) and aromatic hydrocarbons (AH).

468 Carboxylic acids are one of the predominant families in the thermal bio-oils*, acetic acid
469 being the most abundant, which is originated from the thermal decomposition of
470 hemicellulose fragments and cellulose-derived products or by cracking of lignin side
471 chains. The acids concentration gradually decreases with the FW proportion in the
472 feedstock (from 13 to 9 wt.%), which can be related to the lower share of lignocellulosic
473 biopolymers in this bio-waste. The concentration of ketones (7-6 wt.%) and sugars (1-0.1
474 wt.%) also decreases with the proportion of FW in the feedstock, but to a lesser extent
475 than carboxylic acids. In contrast, a noticeable rise is observed in the concentration of
476 furans, varying from 3 wt.% in the case of pure GP feedstock to 7 wt.% with pure FW.
477 This higher share of furans is due to the incremental formation of furfural, furamethanol
478 and hydroxymethylfurfural, in comparison with the experiment performed with pure GP,
479 and the appearance of isosorbide, a bicyclic molecule containing two fused furan rings,
480 whose generation is directly related to the thermal degradation of pectin. The production
481 of this compound in those thermal bio-oils produced from mixtures containing FW is of

482 great interest since it is widely used for the manufacture of plasticizers, solvents, or
483 pharmaceuticals. [42]

484 On the other hand, the concentration of oxygenated aromatic compounds exhibits the
485 highest value (14.8 wt.%) for the thermal experiment of pure GP feedstock. Their
486 concentration drops up to 9 wt.% when a 20 wt.% of FW are introduced in the feed
487 mixture, due to the lower lignin content in this bio-residue. Nevertheless, a slight increase
488 is observed in their concentration when FW shares of 40 and 100 % are introduced in the
489 feed, varying from 9 to 11.5 wt.%. For a more detailed discussion, Fig. 5C depicts the
490 concentration of the most abundant subgroups of OAR: phenols (PHE), guaiacols (GUA),
491 syringols (SYR), catechols (CAT), and methoxybenzenes (METH). As observed, the
492 concentrations of both syringols and methoxybenzenes decreases with the FW share,
493 which are converted into guaiacols or phenols *via* demethoxylation reactions, whose
494 concentrations show an opposite trend. This fact denotes that the formation of these less
495 oxygenated OAR is favoured with the incorporation of FW in the feed mixture.
496 Nevertheless, despite the high concentration of oxygenated aromatics, the presence of
497 aromatic hydrocarbons (AH) is quite small as displayed Fig. 5B (< 0.8 wt.% in the bio-
498 oil*), indicating that the phenolic derivatives are barely deoxygenated by thermal
499 pyrolysis.

500

501 **Fig. 5.** Percentage of bio-oil* quantified by GC–MS in the thermal and catalytic tests (A),
 502 concentration of main compound families in thermal and catalytic bio-oils* (B) and
 503 concentration of main oxygenated aromatics (C) and aromatic hydrocarbons (D)
 504 subfamilies determined by GC-MS.

505

506 The catalyst utilization provokes significant variations in the bio-oil molecular
 507 composition, leading to a sharp decrease in the concentration of carboxylic acids (5-3
 508 wt.%), ketones (6-4.5 wt.%), furans (1.4-1.1 wt.%), and sugars, the latter even becoming
 509 negligible. In contrast, the concentration of oxygenated aromatics increases considerably
 510 in comparison with the thermal experiments, a result that is attributed to a higher degree
 511 of degradation of lignin oligomers over the catalyst. However, their concentration
 512 decreases with the amount of FW in the feed mixture (from 21 to 12 wt.%). Interestingly,

513 despite the decline in the overall concentration of OAR, the concentration of phenols
514 notably increases with the FW proportion achieving values of almost 9.5 wt.% in the case
515 of pure FW feed, while the amount of guaiacols and methoxybenzenes decreases (see Fig.
516 5C). This fact can be related to the catalytic promotion of demethoxylation reactions of
517 the latter derivatives, leading to the formation of valuable phenolics compounds with
518 increasing FW shares. These phenols are mostly composed of cresols (43-48% of PHE),
519 which are priceless compounds to produce solvents, disinfectants, or chemical
520 intermediates for different industrial processes; and phenol (26-34% of PHE), which is
521 also an important industrial chemical precursor to produce resins, plastics, dyes or
522 pharmaceuticals among others.

523 However, the most remarkable result from the catalytic assays is the drastic growth in the
524 production of AH when FW is introduced in the feed, with increasing concentrations from
525 13 to 21 wt.% in the catalytic bio-oil*, becoming eventually the main family in case of
526 using pure FW. Interestingly, these AH are largely composed of MAH such xylenes,
527 trimethylbenzenes and in lesser proportion toluene and benzene, whose overall
528 concentration grows from 10 to 18 wt.% as the FW share increases in the feed, as
529 displayed Fig. 5D. The changes in the chemical composition of the bio-oil* and the higher
530 generation of olefins in the catalytic assays denote that the formation of these valuable
531 compounds could proceed by different reaction paths such as olefins aromatization, OAR
532 deoxygenation and cracking reactions as well as Diels-Alder (DA) condensations, all of
533 them catalyzed by the acid sites of the zeolite. [44-46] Accordingly, an opposite trend is
534 observed in the concentration of OAR and AH, when increasing FW amounts are fed,
535 which may denote that the OAR compounds generated from FW degradation are more
536 susceptible to be deoxygenated. This agrees with the enhanced proportion of phenols and

537 cresols detected in the catalytic bio-oils* obtained from feedstock with higher FW shares.
538 In addition, the strong reduction in the concentration of furans together with the higher
539 generation of olefins in the catalytic assays suggest the occurrence of Diels-Alder (DA)
540 condensation reactions promoted by the acidic zeolite. In this sense, isosorbide, which is
541 formed by the thermal degradation of pectin, acts as an important furan source, promoting
542 the generation of MAH, as is proposed in Fig. 6. To demonstrate the occurrence of this
543 possible reaction pathway, pure isosorbide was pyrolyzed in presence of n-ZSM-5 using
544 a micropyrolyzer system coupled with a GC-MS. The semiquantitative composition of
545 the pyrolysis vapours in terms of the relative area of the GC was plotted in Fig. S5. As
546 observed, the main products obtained were MAH (predominantly toluene, xylenes and
547 alkylbenzenes), which denotes that isosorbide promotes the formation of these valuable
548 compounds under pyrolytic conditions. Nevertheless, the high proportion of furan
549 derivatives (among which furan is the most abundant) suggests that this process proceeds
550 through the conversion of isosorbide into furans, *via* dehydration and cracking reactions,
551 which can subsequently react with the olefins yielding MAH following a Diels Alder
552 route. The production of MAH from isosorbide in presence of ZSM-5 zeolite was also
553 observed by Henri et al. [47]

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560

561 **Fig. 6.** Proposed Diels-Alder (DA) reaction pathway from isosorbide to monoaromatic
 562 hydrocarbons.

563

564 4. Conclusions

565 The co-processing of fruit wastes (one of the largest groups in household food refuse) and
 566 garden pruning residues mixtures presents significant beneficial effects regarding the
 567 individual pyrolysis of both bio-residues. Thus, the presence of fruit wastes in the feed
 568 mixture facilitates the deoxygenation of the pyrolysis vapours, leading to bio-oils* (bio-
 569 oil in water-free basis) with increased HHV in comparison to the pure lignocellulosic
 570 residue as feedstock. In addition, the utilization of a nanocrystalline ZSM-5 zeolite as
 571 catalyst produces important changes in its molecular composition, leading to a sharp
 572 decrease in the concentration of acids, ketones and ethers, furans and sugars, these last
 573 even disappearing. In contrast, a higher concentration of phenol and cresols is observed
 574 due to the catalytic promotion of demethoxylation reactions of heavier phenolic
 575 derivatives. In addition, the incorporation of the catalyst significantly increases the
 576 concentration of monoaromatic aromatic hydrocarbons, which is even more pronounced
 577 with larger shares of FW due to the participation of isosorbide, generated in significant
 578 amounts from pectine thermal degradation. This compound acts a furan source, reacting
 579 with olefins via Diels-Alder condensation over the acidic sites of the zeolite.

580 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

581 The authors state that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
582 relationships that could have influenced the research reported in this manuscript.

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